

Kinetics of the Reaction of 2,3-[3-Norcaren-*endo*-2,5-diyl]-*N*-(2',4'-dinitrophenoxy)succinimide with Hydroxide Ion, Piperidine, Morpholine and Cyclohexylamine. Base Catalysis with Hydroxide Ion and Piperidine

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THE occurrence of base catalysis in nucleophilic substitution reaction¹⁻³ of nitro-activated aromatic substrate depends on the nature of the nucleophile, the leaving group, the solvent and the stability of the intermediate complex. We have studied reaction of 2,3-[9,10-dihydroanthracene-*endo*-9,10-diyl]-*N*-(2',4'-dinitrophenoxy)succinimide in 20-80 (v/v) aqueous-acetonitrile and have observed⁴ catalysis by OH⁻ and piperidine but not by cyclohexylamine (CHA) and morpholine (MOR). When the same reaction was carried out in various non-aqueous media, such as acetonitrile, ethyl acetate, benzene, dioxane and methanol, catalysis by piperidine was observed⁵ in all the cases except in methanol. A review of the literature shows that effect of simple nucleofuge, such as halogen, alkoxy and aryloxy has so far been studied to understand the phenomenon. In this communication, we report the results of our kinetic studies on the title compound possessing sterically congested nucleofuge.

Experimental

1,3,5-Cycloheptatriene-maleic anhydride adduct was converted to 2,3-(3-norcaren-*endo*-2,5-diyl)-*N*-hydroxysuccinimide (1) by treatment⁶ with NH₂OH.HCl and NaOAc. A methanolic solution of the *N*-hydroxy compound (1), 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene and NaOMe in equimolar proportion was warmed for a few minutes and cooled to obtain on recrystallisation from absolute ethanol, colourless crystals of 2,3-[3-norcaren-*endo*-2,5-diyl]-*N*-(2',4'-dinitrophenoxy)succinimide (2), m.p. 226-27°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1750 (C=O), 1525 (C-NO₂) and 1600 (N-O) cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeCN) 245 nm (log ϵ =4.3); δ (CDCl₃); 90

MHz) 0.22 (2H, m), 1.17 (2H, m), 3.14 (2H, m), 3.46 (2H, m), 5.9 (2H, m), 7.2-8.9 (3H, m, aromatic). The reaction was followed in aqueous acetonitrile (20-80, v/v) under pseudo-first order conditions at 35±0.1° and at 360 nm employing a Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The first order rate constants (k_0) were obtained from the plots of log ($A_\infty - A_0$)/($A_\infty - A_t$) vs t (A_∞ , A_0 and A_t represent respectively the absorbances of the reaction mixture at infinity, zero and at time t) and were analysed by least-square curve fitting method using a DEC 2050 computer. The second order rate constants (k_A) were obtained by dividing k_0 by [base] effective.

In all the runs, [substrate] was maintained at 4×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³. However, it was not possible to have [base] in the same range in all the cases. To keep the reaction at a measurable rate, relatively high [base] was used in the case of CHA and MOR. The negligible variation in rate observed in these two cases, however, does not seem to be due to saturation effect.

The reaction products were found to be 2,4-dinitrophenol, *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)morpholine, *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)cyclohexylamine, *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)piperidine with OH⁻, morpholine, cyclohexylamine and piperidine respectively, together with the parent *N*-hydroxy compound (1) in each case. The spectral, tlc and m.p. data were identical with those of the authentic samples.

Results and Discussion

The values of k_A for the reaction of hydroxide ion and piperidine steadily increased with increased base concentration. However, in the case of morpholine and cyclohexylamine, negligible variation occurred in k_A values (Table 1). The plots of k_A vs [OH⁻] and also [piperidine] were linear with positive slopes and intercepts. The reactions are,

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_A) FOR REACTION OF 2 WITH BASES IN AQUEOUS ACETONITRILE (20-80, v/v)

[Substrate]= 4×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³, Temp.=35±0.1°

10 ⁴ [OH ⁻] mol dm ³	3.0	4.0	5.0	6.0	6.5	7.0
10 ⁴ k_A dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	3.7	4.8	5.0	5.9	6.3	6.9
10 ⁴ [MOR] mol dm ⁻³	5.5	11.0	16.5	22.0	27.5	—
10 ⁴ k_A dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	3.8	3.8	3.6	4.0	4.0	—
10 ⁴ [CHA] mol dm ⁻³	29.5	44.3	59.0	73.8	88.5	—
10 ⁴ k_A dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	5.1	5.2	4.9	5.1	5.1	—
10 ⁴ [Piperidine] mol dm ⁻³	4.9	5.5	6.2	6.8	8.0	8.6
10 ⁴ k_A dm ³ mol ⁻¹	13.9	15.3	16.4	16.8	20.0	22.6

therefore, base-catalysed^{2,3}. The experimental rate law follows equation (1),

$$k_A = k' + k'' [B] \quad (1)$$

where, [B] is the base present, k' the intercept ($=k_1 k_2 / k_{-1}$), is the non-catalytic and k'' the slope ($=k_1 k_3 / k_{-1}$), the catalytic rate constant. Scheme 1 is a possible interpretation of equation (1).

Scheme 1

The extent of acceleration by bases conveniently expressed as k''/k' , representing the relative magnitude of the accelerated and unaccelerated parts of the reaction at 1M base concentration, is almost negligible for MOR and CHA reactions but is very high in the case of hydroxide ion and piperidine (k''/k' values 4800 and 7000 respectively) indicating true base-catalysis in these cases⁴. Taking into consideration the pK_a values of morpholine (8.2), cyclohexylamine (9.6) and piperidine (10.2) in aqueous acetonitrile (20–80, v/v), a close scrutiny of the appropriate intermediate complex (Scheme 1) would suggest that the complexes obtained from MOR and CHA would deprotonate (the hydrogen on the ammonium nitrogen atom of the complex) relatively easily than those of the hydroxide ion and piperidine. This deprotonation makes the reversal step (k_{-1}) more difficult but the departure of the leaving group easier. The oxygen atom of the *N*-hydroxy function of the leaving group may also be protonated in a subsequent fast step and facilitate removal of the leaving group unaided by base following a non-catalysed path as shown in Scheme 2 for the morpholine reaction.

On the other hand, σ -complexes derived from hydroxide ion and piperidine (higher pK_a values) do not deprotonate so easily as a result the reversal step is more facilitated. The presence of additional base molecules helps deprotonate the intermediate complex and pave the way for the departure of the leaving group with consequent base-catalysis. It is

Scheme 2

observed that rate constant for OH⁻ reaction is lower than that of piperidine. This is understandable in the light of HSAB principle. Hydroxide ion is relatively hard compared to piperidine as a base and the reaction site (aromatic carbon) is relatively soft. A study of the effect of temperature showed high negative value of entropy of activation in each case as envisaged.

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